

Fear of evaluation unpacked: Day to day correlates of fear of negative and
positive evaluation

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Abstract

Background and objectives: Social interactions inevitably go along with repeated evaluations. Some individuals are particularly sensitive to social evaluations: Psychometric studies suggest stable and distinct individual differences on fear of negative evaluations (FNE) and positive evaluation (FPE). However, little is known about day to day correlates of FNE and FPE, particularly their respective contribution to positive/negative affect level and affect reactivity to different stressor types.

Design: Two studies naturalistically assessed the *level* of negative/positive affect and its *reactivity* to different stressor types (from distant or close social network, work and daily hassles, assessed daily) as a function of FNE/FPE.

Method: Ecological Momentary Assessment employed five daily prompts during 12/10 days in convenience samples of 50/59 participants.

Results: FNE predicted lower positive affect level only in Study 2. Consistent across studies negative affect reactivity to stressors emanating from the distant social network was increased in individuals high in FNE or FPE.

Conclusions: Results document the relevance of both types of evaluation fears (FNE/FPE) for day to day affect and stress reactivity. They further specify whose evaluations are well tolerated (close network) or feared (distant network), thereby refining current psycho-evolutionary accounts of FNE/FPE.

Keywords: emotional reactivity; affect; social situations; stress; social anxiety

Introduction

Social evaluations are an integral part of day-to-day interactions in social groups (Schoeneman, 1983). They are also a means of hierarchically organizing social networks (Dickerson, Gruenewald, & Kemeny, 2004). According to Gilbert (2014) closely monitoring these evaluations in order to appropriately regulate behavior might have been evolutionary advantageous. Certain individuals, however, exhibit particularly strong and stable, fearful cognitions regarding the consequences of such evaluations. Such pronounced fears of evaluation were shown to go along with negative consequences in several domains of social, emotional and cognitive functioning (Reichenberger & Blechert, submitted), which has intrigued researchers from several domains alike and motivated additional research on the nature and correlates of such evaluation centered fears.

Fear of negative evaluation (FNE) was originally defined as a trait related to “apprehension about others’ evaluations, distress over their negative evaluations, avoidance of evaluative situations, and the expectation that others would evaluate oneself negatively” (Watson & Friend, 1969; p. 449). FNE lies at the core of most conceptualizations of social anxiety (e.g., Clark & Wells, 1995; Heimberg, Brozovich, & Rapee, 2010). More recently, a complementary construct was introduced, *fear of positive evaluation* (FPE), described as feelings of discomfort in face of favorable evaluation, associated cognitions and behavioral avoidance of such occasions. This less intuitive component of social anxiety is explained in a psycho-evolutionary framework. Accordingly, positive evaluation results in a relative upward shift in the social hierarchy, thereby bringing the individual in conflict with higher ranking group members (Gilbert, 2001, 2014; Weeks, Heimberg, & Rodebaugh, 2008; Weeks & Howell, 2012). Hence, FPE, by avoiding positive evaluations, serves to avoid upward hierarchical movements and ensures a stable intermediate position in social hierarchy and protection from rank-related conflict. The same

psycho-evolutionary account explains that negative evaluations decrease social status (commensurate to social rank) with the risk of ultimate social exclusion. Thus, FNE supposedly serves to avoid downward shifts in social hierarchy. Albeit related (and often positively correlated), FNE and FPE have been repeatedly shown to resemble partially independent and unique constructs (e.g., Reichenberger, Wiggert, Wilhelm, Weeks, & Blechert, 2015; Weeks et al., 2008). That is, each explain independent variance in socially anxious behaviors, but produce particularly pronounced impairments when occurring together (Lipton, Weeks, & De Los Reyes, 2016). In fact, impairments in individuals with FNE and FPE have been reported in various domains (e.g., cognitive and behavioral), yet research on emotional correlates from externally valid assessment approaches is limited (Reichenberger & Blechert, submitted).

What is known about emotional correlates of FPE and FNE emanates from two research lines: A psychometric research line has shown that both FNE and FPE go along with generally higher negative and generally lower positive affect (i.e. Positive and Negative Affect Scale scores)(Wang, Hsu, Chiu, & Liang, 2012; Weeks & Howell, 2012; Weeks, Jakatdar, & Heimberg, 2010). Thus, this research line suggests a general shift of *affective level* (that is, generally higher negative and lower positive affect intensity) in individuals with high FNE and FPE without further specifying sources or triggers of such affects. A second, mainly laboratory-based research line followed a symptom-provocation paradigm and examined whether standardized social stimuli elicited increased affective responses in individuals with elevated levels on each (FNE/FPE) fear component. Following this *affective reactivity* research line, Weeks and Zoccola (2015) used a standardized social stress test (i.e. an evaluated speech) and showed that FPE and FNE were each uniquely linked to elevated anxiety and elevated negative affect reactivity. Even more control was implemented in the studies of Weeks, Howell, and Goldin (2013) and Reichenberger et al. (2015), each using videos clips depicting standardized

negative and positive evaluative sentences. In both studies enhanced affective reactivity (i.e. increase of state anxiety, unpleasantness ratings, respectively) was documented. Although validating the concepts of FNE and FPE, neither line of research optimized external validity. That is, actual daily experiences are not directly taken into account, nor are naturalistic triggers of affective reactivity known.

Here, ecological momentary assessment (EMA) affords new ways to model both general affective level (in the sense of ‘baseline’ affect) and affective reactivity (i.e. transient responses to specific environmental factors) under naturalistic conditions (Shiffman, Stone, & Hufford, 2008; Smyth, Juth, Ma, & Sliwinski, 2017). Thus, in the current studies we addressed an *affective level* research question by examining whether FNE and FPE affect daily reports of positive affect and negative affect in EMA. We expected both, FNE and FPE, to potentiate negative affect and attenuate positive affect in general. The EMA method further allows to examine the effects of various *stressor types* on affective responses as a function of FNE or FPE, thereby testing the *affective reactivity* hypothesis. In fact, the questions of *what or who* triggers emotional reactivity in FNE/FPE has been neglected so far. Although theoretical accounts of FNE and FPE imply that only social situations should provoke the respective fears (e.g., Watson & Friend, 1969; Weeks et al., 2008), this prediction remains to be tested. Affect might also respond to stressors that are not explicitly social, such as work stress and daily hassles. Furthermore, even within the social domain, it remains unclear which social networks would be particularly impactful. In current theories it is not specified which group (and respective hierarchy) should be of concern. Individuals are members of several, partially overlapping groups, ranging from family members to peers, work colleagues and larger groups (e.g., nationality, gender, or ethnicity) (e.g., Settles & Buchanan, 2014). Thus, we addressed the *affective reactivity* question separately for the four broadly defined stressor types ‘close social network’, ‘wider social network’, ‘work stress’ and

‘daily hassles’. We expected positive affect to decrease and negative affect to increase on days with elevated social stressors (either from closer or wider social networks) in individuals with either high FNE or high FPE. With regard to the theoretical specification of both evaluative fears to social situations, no such relationships were expected for work stress and daily hassles.

Last, to increase specificity to the anxiety domain, depressive symptoms and gender will be included as control variables. Depression has frequently been linked to altered emotional experiences (Bylsma, Morris, & Rottenberg, 2008) that overlap with symptoms of social anxiety (as well as its cognitive components FNE and FPE) (e.g., see ‘the tripartite model of anxiety and depression of Clark & Watson, 1991 or Watson, 2005; for a theoretical overlap; see Reichenberger, Wiggert, Agroskin, Wilhelm, & Blechert, 2017; for an experimental overlap). Gender was included as a control variable as female individuals have been found to exhibit higher prevalence rates of social anxiety disorder (e.g., Merikangas et al., 2010) and differences between both sexes with regard to emotional reactivity have frequently been found (e.g., Bradley, Codispoti, Sabatinelli, & Lang, 2001; Kelly, Tyrka, Anderson, Price, & Carpenter, 2008; Lithari et al., 2010). In addition, to increase replicability and generalizability, a two study design was chosen: In Study 1 we examined a predominantly student sample, whereas in Study 2 we obtained a predominantly non-student sample (with higher heterogeneity on participant age and profession). In Study 2 the breadth of the emotion assessment was also extended by distinguishing between high and low arousal emotions in the positive and negative valence domain, based on a circumplex model of affect (Russell, 1980).

Study 1

Method

Participants

Fifty-three predominantly undergraduate (94%) participants participated in exchange for course credit or payment (compliance dependent remuneration of 30-50€). After the data collection phase, three individuals were excluded because of overall low compliance rates (< 50%). The final sample of 50 individuals (66% female) reported a mean age of 23.6 ($SD = 2.75$). Participants signed a consent form approved by the ethics committee of the University of Salzburg.

Questionnaires

The *Brief Fear of Evaluation Scale – Revised* (BFNE-R; Carleton, McCreary, Norton, & Asmundson, 2006) is a measure to assess fear and distress related to negative evaluation from others and support for its validity was found. In the present study three items (item 1, 4 and 6) with the highest factor loading and item discrimination were used to reduce participant's burden. Item selection was based on a study with a convenience sample of 414 participants (307 females; mean age 26.7, $SD = 8.20$) collected for the validation of the German version of the questionnaire (Reichenberger, Schwarz, et al., 2016). The three items (e.g., "I am usually worried about what kind of impression I make") are self-rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (*not at all characteristic of me*) – 5 (*extremely characteristic of me*). The sum ranges from 3 to 15, with higher scores indicating higher FNE. The version used in the current sample showed good internal consistency ($\alpha = .86$).

Similarly, the *Fear of Positive Evaluation Scale* (FPES; Weeks et al., 2008) is a measure to assess fear and distress related to positive evaluation from others and support for its validity was found. In the present study three items (item 2, 4 and 8) with the highest factor loading and item discrimination were used to reduce participant's burden. Item selection was based on a study with a convenience sample of 414 participants (307 females; mean age 26.7, $SD = 8.20$) collected for the validation of the German version of the questionnaire (Schwarz et al., 2016). The three

items (e.g., “I feel uneasy when I receive praise from authority figures.”) are self-rated on a 10-point Likert scale from 0 (*not at all true*) to 9 (*very true*). The sum ranges from 0 to 27, with higher scores indicating higher FPE. The version used in the current sample showed acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = .69$). Consistent with prior work, the correlation between FPE and FNE was $r(50) = .460, p = .001$.

The *Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale* (CESD; Radloff, 1977) measures subjective impairments associated with depressive symptoms within the last week. The short version comprises 15 items (e.g., “I felt depressed”) that are rated on a 4-point scale from 0 (*rarely or not at all/less than one day*) – 3 (*most, all of the time/5 to 7 days*). The sum scores range from 0 to 45, with higher scores denoting higher depression severity. The German version has demonstrated construct validity (Hautzinger, Bailer, Hofmeister, & Keller, 2012) and in the present sample good internal consistency ($\alpha = .89$).

EMA measures: emotions and stressor types

At each of 5 intraday signals, participants completed questions about positive and negative affect. Emotions were assessed on visual-analogue scales consisting of continuous horizontal rating sliders ranging from 0 - 100 (not at all – very much), with participants being asked ‘How do you feel right now?’ followed by a list of two positive and negative emotion items each (cheerful, active; irritated, distressed)¹. Stressor types were retrospectively assessed at the end of the day by asking participants to report how stressed they felt that day because of either *work, close social network, distant social network* or *daily hassles* on similar visual-analogue scales (0 = not at all to 100 = very much).

Procedure

¹ Within-person reliability was assessed using variance decomposition technique (see Shrout & Lane, 2012). Within-person reliability was moderate for positive affect ($R_c = .65$) and fair for negative affect ($R_c = .58$) according to Shrout (1998).

After completing initial questionnaires about demographic information at an online survey platform, participants were personally or via telephone instructed on the installation of the PsyDiary app (developed by the department of MultiMediaTechnology of the Salzburg University of Applied Sciences) on their smartphones. After one practice day (data not used in the study), ensuring familiarity with the app and to reduce any short-term measurement reactivity, participants completed six days of EMA. In an attempt to increase variability in stress experiences, participants chose one week of EMA in a presumptively high stress period (mainly during exam period at the end of a semester) and one week in a presumptively low stress period (mainly at the beginning of a semester). After the first week of EMA, participants completed several additional questionnaires (among them questionnaires to assess FNE and FPE) and resumed the data collection roughly 2.5 months after. Again, after one practice day (data not used), participants completed six days of EMA. In order to control for carry-over effects between the sample periods, 32 participants started with their low-stress and 18 participants started in their high-stress week. In a final questionnaire we included questions about potential reactivity.

Signal-contingent sampling was used, with five equidistant prompts at 10 a.m., 1 p.m., 4 p.m., 7 p.m., and 10 p.m. Diary entries could be delayed if safety was a concern (e.g., while driving) or when there was no possibility to reply (for up to one hour, with or without reminders every 10 minutes). In addition to signal-contingent reports, event-sampling was also used, asking participants to fill out an evening questionnaire shortly before they go to sleep.

Plan of Analyses

For every signal, negative and positive affect were calculated by taking the mean of the two negative and two positive emotion items, respectively. To obtain daily negative and positive affect, the mean of all intraday signals (on negative or positive affect) was computed.

Hierarchical linear models were calculated using the software HLM7 (Raudenbush, Byrk, & Congdon, 2011) because of the nested, longitudinal structure of the data. Occasions/daily data (Level 1) were nested within participants (Level 2). To examine the *affective level hypothesis*, we separately predicted daily negative and positive affect (signals averaged within days) and included FNE and FPE separately as Level 2 predictors of the intercept. Additionally, to test the *affective reactivity hypothesis*, i.e. the question whether different stressor types differentially impacted affect as a function of FNE/FPE, we separately predicted negative and positive affect by each of the four stressor types on Level 1 and included FNE and FPE separately as Level 2 predictors of the intercept as well as moderators of the Level 1 slopes (e.g., negative affect predicted by work stress on Level 1 and FNE included as Level 2 predictor of the intercept as well as moderator of the Level 1 slope). Significant moderations were followed-up with simple slope tests. Slopes were allowed to vary randomly across participants. Level 1 predictors were person-mean centered, Level 2 predictors were grand-mean centered. To control for gender and depressive symptoms, all analyses were rerun with gender (uncentered and coded with female = 1, male = -1) and depressive symptoms (grand-mean centered) as predictors of the intercepts.

Results

EMA measures

On average participants demonstrated very good compliance, completing 88.1% ($SD = 11.1\%$) of their intraday signals (range 57% – 100%), and 86.2% ($SD = 13.1\%$) of the end-of-the-day event-contingent entries (range 50% – 100%). Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation of all variables.

Affective level hypothesis - FNE/FPE and daily affect level

Models were set up as follows, exemplified here for FNE predicting negative affect level:

Level 1:

$$\text{Negative affect}_{ij} = \pi_{0j} + e_{ij}$$

Level 2:

$$\pi_{0j} = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01} (\text{FNE}_j) + r_{0j}$$

Results of Study 1 showed that FNE did not predict overall negative affect level ($\beta_{01} = .729, p = .103$), or positive affect level ($\beta_{01} = .417, p = .512$). Similarly, FPE was predictive of neither negative ($\beta_{01} = .265, p = .439$) nor positive affect level ($\beta_{01} = -.220, p = .577$).²

Affective reactivity to stress – FNE/FPE as moderators of the relationship between daily affect level and stressor type

The next set of analyses examined the associations of daily stressor type with daily negative and positive affect level and explored the role of FNE and FPE as moderators of these relationships.

Level 1 model, exemplified with work stress as a predictor of negative affect level:

$$\text{Negative affect}_{ij} = \pi_{0j} + \pi_{1j} (\text{Stress with work}_{ij}) + e_{ij}$$

Level 2 model, exemplified with FNE as predictor and moderator:

$$\pi_{0j} = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01} (\text{FNE}_j) + r_{0j}$$

$$\pi_{1j} = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11} (\text{FNE}_j) + r_{1j}$$

FNE did not moderate the relationship between stress with work, the close social network or daily hassles (all β_{11} s $< .002, ps > .471$). However, FNE significantly moderated the relationship between stress with the distant social network and negative affect level ($\beta_{11} = .031, p = .037$): Higher stress with the distant social network was associated with stronger negative affect level on that day, but only in individuals high in FNE, $\beta = .109, SE = .033, t_{(48)} = 3.32, p = .002$, (Figure 1). Meanwhile, low-FNE individuals showed the opposite direction in that higher stress

² Results pattern and significance did not change when controlling for gender and depressive symptoms.

with distant social network was associated with less negative affect level on that day, however, not-significantly ($\beta = -.075$, $SE = .084$, $t_{(48)} = -.895$, $p = .375$).

Likewise, FPE did not moderate the relationships between negative affect level and stress with work, the close social network and daily hassles (all $\beta_{11}s < -.004$, $ps > .157$). As with FNE, however, the moderation of the effect from the distant social network was significant ($\beta_{11} = .014$, $p = .033$): in individuals with higher FPE higher distant social network stress went along with more negative affect, $\beta = .105$, $SE = .045$, $t_{(48)} = 2.35$, $p = .023$, whereas low-FPE individuals showed no association between such stress and negative affect level ($\beta = -.021$, $SE = .057$, $t_{(48)} = -.375$, $p = .709$) (Figure 1). When both FNE and FPE were used as simultaneous predictors, neither moderation remained significant (FNE: $\beta_{12} = .027$, $p = .105$; FPE: $\beta_{11} = .004$, $p = .536$), indicating substantial shared variance between FNE and FPE in this association.

Finally, none of the relationships between the four stressors and positive affect level were moderated by FNE (all $\beta_{11}s < .007$, $ps > .487$) or FPE (all $\beta_{11}s < .009$, $ps > .137$).³

Discussion Study 1

Results of Study 1 revealed that neither FNE nor FPE showed a general relationship with overall negative or positive affect level (i.e., providing no evidence for the affective level hypothesis). However, there was a specific association between negative affect level and stress from the distant social network if individuals were either high in FNE or high in FPE (evidence consistent with affective reactivity). In contrast, stress with other stressor types and its relationships with negative or positive affect level were not moderated by FNE or FPE.

Study 2 was conducted as a conceptual replication and extension of Study 1 findings, and to test generalizability to a more diverse sample (notably in terms of age and occupational). Moreover, the *affective level hypothesis* was specified more precisely by splitting negative and

³ Result pattern and significance did not change when controlling for gender and depressive symptoms.

positive emotions according to their arousal level. Previous laboratory research suggests a role of arousal level: FNE/FPE correlated with self-reported and psychophysiological (heart rate) arousal in social stress tasks (Carter, Sbrocco, Riley, & Mitchell, 2012; Weeks & Zoccola, 2015, 2016; Wiggert, Wilhelm, Reichenberger, & Blechert, 2015).

Study 2

Method

Participants

Via several newspaper articles, a television report and word of mouth, participants from Germany and Austria were recruited into a study of “stress and eating in daily life” (eating-related EMA data reported elsewhere⁴). Sixty participants took part in the EMA study in exchange for individualized feedback or payment (compliance dependent remuneration of 35-60€). After the data collection phase, one individual was excluded because of low compliance rate (< 50%). The final sample of 59 individuals (78% female) had a mean age of 39.9 ($SD = 11.9$) with a wide range from 14 to 65 years, with many employees (49%). Participants signed a consent form approved by the ethics committee of the University of Salzburg.

Questionnaires

In Study 2 the same questionnaires as Study 1 were used. As in Study 1, FPE and FNE were assessed with three items of the respective questionnaires. Good internal consistencies for all three measures, the *Brief Fear of Negative Evaluation Scale – Revised* ($\alpha = .85$), the *Fear of Positive Evaluation Scale* ($\alpha = .81$), and the *Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale* ($\alpha = .82$), were obtained in the current study. The correlation between FPE and FNE was $r(59) = .275, p = .035$.

EMA measures

⁴ See (Reichenberger, Kuppens, et al., 2016) for a publication about the eating-related questions.

Measures were identical to Study 1 with the following exceptions: 1) The list of emotions was increased to five positive (cheerful, enthusiastic, awake, calm, relaxed) and five negative (irritated, distressed, bored, nervous/stressed, depressed) emotions each. Emotion items were chosen to represent high and low arousing positive/negative emotions⁵. 2) Different stressor types were assessed at the last signal of the day (9 p.m.).

Procedure

After completing initial questionnaires about demographic information at an online survey platform, participants were instructed via telephone on the installation of the PsyDiary app on their smartphones. After one to two practice days (data not used), ensuring familiarity with the app and to minimize short-term measurement reactivity, participants were contacted again to clarify remaining questions. Afterwards, participants completed 10 days of EMA. A final questionnaire included questions about reactivity. The sampling plan was similar to Study 1, however, only signal-contingent sampling was used, with five equidistant prompts starting somewhat earlier in the day (9 a.m., 12 a.m., 3 p.m., 6 p.m., and 9 p.m.).

Plan of Analyses

For every signal, negative and positive affect scores were calculated by taking the mean of the five negative and positive emotion items, respectively. Signal-wise affect scores were then averaged across all intra-day signals to obtain day level affect scores. Additionally, arousal-sorted scores were further computed as follows: a negative/high arousal score was created from items 'irritated' and 'nervous/stressed'; a negative/low arousal score from 'distressed' and 'depressed';

⁵ Within-person reliability was assessed using variance decomposition technique (see Shrout & Lane, 2012). Within-person reliability was moderate for positive affect ($R_c = .73$) and negative affect ($R_c = .62$) according to Shrout (1998). In addition, within-person reliability was enhanced when affect was split according to the arousal-level: positive/high arousal ($R_c = .74$), positive/low arousal ($R_c = .76$), negative/high arousal ($R_c = .64$), and negative/low arousal ($R_c = .71$).

a positive/high arousal score from ‘cheerful’ and ‘enthusiastic’ as well as a positive/low arousal score from ‘relaxed’ and ‘calm’. Aggregation into day level scores was similar as in Study 1.

Statistical modeling was analogous to Study 1 with the exception that we reran the *affective level hypothesis* in auxiliary analyses using the differentiation of high and low arousal negative and positive emotions.

Results

EMA measures

On average, participants completed 83.6% ($SD = 12.3\%$) of their intraday signals (range 50 – 100%), and 86.4% ($SD = 14.1\%$) of the last signal of the day (range 50 – 100%), demonstrating good compliance. Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation of all variables.

Affective level hypothesis - FNE/FPE and daily affect level

Results showed that FNE did not predict overall negative affect level ($\beta_{01} = -.136, p = .771$), however, higher FNE predicted less positive affect level ($\beta_{01} = -1.14, p = .021$). FPE predicted neither negative ($\beta_{01} = -.050, p = .793$) nor positive affect level ($\beta_{01} = -.212, p = .424$). To provide more insight in specific emotions that might be affected by FNE and FPE, we further split emotion items according to their arousal. This supplemental analysis revealed that the effect of FNE on positive affect was mainly driven by diminished low arousal positive affect level (see Table 2).⁶

Affective reactivity hypothesis – FNE/FPE as moderators of the relationship between daily affect level and stressor type

As in Study 1, the next set of analyses examined the potential moderating role of FNE and FPE on the association of the different stressor types with daily negative and positive affect level. FNE again failed to moderate relationships between stress with work, the close social network or

⁶ Result pattern and significance remained the same when controlling for gender and depressive symptoms. Only the relationship between low-arousing positive emotions and FNE was reduced to non-significance $\beta_{01} = -1.38, p = .077$.

daily hassles (all $\beta_{11s} < .008$, $ps > .148$). Consistent with Study 1, however, FNE moderated the relationship between stress with the distant social network and negative affect level ($\beta_{11} = .022$, $p = .017$). Higher stress with the distant social network went along with higher negative affect level on that day, especially in individuals high in FNE ($\beta = .148$, $SE = .040$, $t_{(57)} = 3.70$, $p < .001$). In contrast, low-FNE individuals showed only slightly higher negative affect level corresponding to reports of distant social network stress, however, not significantly, $\beta = .010$, $SE = .036$, $t_{(57)} = .270$, $p = .788$, (Figure 2).

Likewise, FPE did not moderate any of the relationships between stress with work, the close social network and daily hassles with negative affect level (all $\beta_{11s} < .002$, $ps > .239$). However, FPE again significantly moderated the association between stress with the distant social network and negative affect level ($\beta_{11} = .008$, $p = .011$). Thereby, in individuals with higher FPE higher stress went along with more negative affect level ($\beta = .128$, $SE = .036$, $t_{(57)} = 3.55$, $p < .001$), whereas low FPE individuals showed no association between stress and negative affect ($\beta = .010$, $SE = .032$, $t_{(57)} = .326$, $p = .746$) (Figure 2). As both components, FNE and FPE, moderated this relationship, they were considered simultaneously: this time, both moderators remained significant (FPE: $\beta_{11} = .007$, $p = .019$; FNE: $\beta_{12} = .019$, $p = .024$). Hence, we tested in an exploratory fashion for a significant interaction of FNE and FPE (z-standardized) and revealed interesting results: The interaction significantly moderated the association between stress with the distant social network with negative affect level (FNE*FPE*distant social network stress: $\beta_{13} = .088$, $p < .001$). As stress with the distant social network increases, negative affect increases, and this relationship was strongest (steepest slope) and significant in individuals high in both FNE and FPE ($\beta = .277$, $SE = .033$, $t_{(55)} = 8.37$, $p < .001$), lowest in individuals low in both FNE and FPE, and intermediate for those with either high FNE or high FPE (all $\beta s < .039$, $ps > .307$) (Figure 3).

In addition, FNE did not moderate the relationships between stress with work, the close or distant social network, daily hassles and positive affect level (all $\beta_{11s} < .013$, $ps > .057$). Similarly, FPE did not moderate the relationships between any stressor type and positive affect level (all $\beta_{11s} < .002$, $ps > .084$).⁷

Discussion Study 2

Similar to Study 1, FNE did not show a general association with negative affect level, in that across all days combined, individuals with higher FNE did not have elevated or reduced negative affect. Neither did FPE show a general association with daily negative and positive affect level, in that across all study days combined, individuals with higher scores on FPE did not have elevated or reduced negative or positive affect. Further replicating results of Study 1 with regard to the affective reactivity hypothesis, the associations between negative and positive affect levels with work stress, daily hassles and stress with the close social network were not moderated by FNE or FPE. Importantly, the relationship of daily stress with the distant social network and negative affect level was again moderated by FNE and FPE. Above person average stress with the distant social network went along with above person average negative affect levels, especially pronounced in individuals high in FNE or FPE. Exploring their interaction revealed that particularly in individuals high in both FNE and FPE above person average levels of negative affect went along with above person average levels of stress with the distant social network. Unlike Study 1, however, higher FNE related to lower daily positive affect level, which seems to be due to diminished low-arousal positive affect. Of note, including gender and depression as control variables reduced the result to non-significance.

Overall Discussion

⁷ Result patterns and significance remained the same controlling for gender and depression.

Extending previous work that has used psychometric and experimental methods, the current study was the first to apply EMA methodology to determine the relevance of both FNE and FPE for day to day experiences. Specifically, in the studies we modeled the impact of FNE and FPE on daily negative and positive affect *level* (affective level hypothesis) as well as affective *reactivity* to four different stressor types (affective reactivity hypothesis).

In contrast to some previous studies, the evidence for the *affective level hypothesis* was equivocal in daily life. Study 1 did not yield any relationships between FNE or FPE and daily negative or positive affect level, whereas Study 2 revealed a negative relationship between FNE and positive affect that was partially carried by depression and gender. Much previous research and theorizing document low positive affect in both depression and social anxiety (e.g., Anderson & Hope, 2008; Wang et al., 2012). This is reflected in the present data showing that adding depression to the model renders the FNE – low arousing negative affect finding non-significant. Thus, shared variance might account for this finding. Supporting the current results, an experimental study showed that self-calmness associations (i.e. low-arousing positive affect) are especially weak in individuals with comorbid social anxiety disorder and depression, compared to socially anxious without depression (Wong, Morrison, Heimberg, Goldin, & Gross, 2014) speaking to the intricate linkage between depression and anxiety with regard to affect. Thus, the link between FNE with general affective experience seems to be less specific to fears of evaluation alone but rather represents the outcome of factors that often covary in subclinical and clinical samples (comorbidity between social anxiety and depressive disorders; e.g., Fava et al., 2000; Fehm, Beesdo, Jacobi, & Fiedler, 2008; Ohayon & Schatzberg, 2010). However, not only sample composition but also the breadth of affect assessment differed between the two studies, warranting further examination of this link. Nevertheless, diminished positive affect level in individuals with pronounced FNE is generally in line with previous research (Wang et al., 2012;

Weeks, 2015; Weeks & Howell, 2012; Weeks et al., 2010). The absence of an association between FPE and negative/positive affect level contrasts with our hypotheses and several psychometric studies (e.g., Wang et al., 2012; Weeks & Howell, 2012; Weeks et al., 2010). Both samples, however, scored rather low on FPE, warranting further investigations in samples with higher FPE scores.

In line with the *affective reactivity hypothesis*, and consistent across studies, days characterized by higher stress with members of the distant social network were characterized by higher negative affect levels, especially in individuals with high FNE and high FPE. Furthermore, in line with Lipton et al. (2016) but extending this work to daily life, Study 2 points to mutual ‘amplification’ of FNE and FPE. That is, the stressor–affect link is strongest when both constructs are high, weak when both are low, and intermediate when either FNE or FPE alone is high. The absence of this pattern for stress with work or daily hassles provides specificity for social situations and therefore the conceptualization of FNE and FPE. That is, in line with the diagnostic criterion of social anxiety disorder, exemplifying anxiety eliciting situation as meeting *unfamiliar* people (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013), current results yielded consistent alterations in stress with the wider social network. Also FPE items portray situations with individuals that are not known very well (Schwarz et al., 2016; Weeks et al., 2008) and thus our results might reflect this wording and conceptualization.

The selectiveness of fears of evaluation related affective reactivity to members of the distant social network (as opposed to any network member) may lie in the nature of the relationships. Explanations for this finding can be drawn from two literatures. According to the clinical literature, namely, cognitive models of social anxiety (Clark & Wells, 1995), socially anxious individuals form conditional beliefs about the consequences of their actions in social situations (e.g., “If people get to know me, they won’t like me”). Such responses might be less

likely and more predictable within the closer social network. Furthermore, avoiding contact with members of the close compared to the distant social network seems more difficult, so that potentially individuals with FNE/FPE might have habituated to social encounters with family members and friends. According to literature from non-clinical samples, daily stress with family members is less distressing than stress with other persons because conflicts are contextualized within more stable relationships with a lower likelihood of terminal conflict escalation and separation (Bolger, DeLongis, Kessler, & Schilling, 1989). Drawing more from the psycho-evolutionary accounts introduced above, one could expect the wider social network to be a relevant peer group that uses evaluations to rank and organize resources in that group. The close social network, by contrast, might be less hierarchically organized. Previous research showed that individuals with social anxiety tend to over-utilize a social rank system to organize their environment (e.g., Weisman, Aderka, Marom, Hermesh, & Gilboa-Schechtman, 2011). The present results further suggest that closeness/distance of the respective group matters. To follow up on such reasoning, future research would profit from more information on social network members (core family, more remote relatives, peers, coworkers, etc.) and the types of relationships (emotional, instrumental, informational, professional, etc.) to gain specificity on anxiety triggers in individuals with high FNE and/or FPE.

Limitations and Future Directions

Although presenting novel information and generally replicating findings across two studies, there are a number of limitations to this work. First, stress in different occasions was only measured once at the end of the day, preventing us from directly relating current emotional states to recent stressor episodes. Hence, future research should assess stressful episodes at a higher frequency within day to allow for stronger predictive analyses. In addition, affect was assessed signal-based throughout the day, potentially missing out on affective reactivity to some stressors

that are more likely to accumulate at certain time intervals (i.e., commute in mornings/evenings). Likewise, signal-based sampling was not randomized, making prompts easier to predict for participants. Thus, stressful episodes and related affect could also be measured event-based, context-triggered or with randomized prompts in future research. In addition, Study 1 used a two-week design to obtain naturalistically varying stress intensity, however, the small number of occasions (6 per week) prevented us from separately analyzing and comparing both weeks. However, future research might profit from a two-week design in case of a higher sampling frequency. Second, incorporating questions more precisely assessing stressor situation characteristics (e.g., social versus non-social; perceived audience) could further aid in decomposing occasions relevant for FNE and FPE. For example, work stressors could be characterized by workload (not relevant for FNE/FPE) or conflicts with colleagues (relevant for FNE/FPE), and a reproach by the boss could be during a private face-to-face interaction or in front of colleagues, thus amplifying the damage to one's social rank. Additionally, participants subjectively classified stress with other individuals into stress with the close or distant social network, potentially affecting our results. Thus, as mentioned above, collecting more information about this classification process (i.e. who is part of the close versus distant social network and why) will benefit our understanding of social threat reactivity in FNE/FPE. Third, FPE and FNE were measured with a selection of three items of their validated questionnaires each. Although internal consistencies were acceptable to good, future studies should replicate findings using the complete questionnaires. Fourth, to tap more directly into FPE, future research could track positive social evaluative situations more directly, by asking participants about daily praise or classifying social interactions via event-contingent sampling as positive vs. negative. Fifth, future research could explore gender as moderator. We had evaluated gender as control variable and thus not focused on this variable in detail. Yet, this might be worthwhile, for example, females

have higher scores on FPE (e.g., Teale Sapach, Carleton, Mulvogue, Weeks, & Heimberg, 2015) and thus, its moderations of daily affective dynamics might also differ by gender.

Conclusions

To conclude, this work adds to a growing body of literature in support of FNE and FPE as key constructs in human social organization, anxiety and affect with relevance to clinical and non-clinical (social) anxiety. Individuals experiencing high levels of FPE and FNE respond to social stress experiences with negative affect ‘bouts’, underscoring the need for emotion regulation and skill trainings for these specific situations. Intervening on FNE and FPE could be of relevance not only for social anxiety disorder, but also for other psychological disorders that exhibit elevated levels of FNE or FPE (see Reichenberger & Blechert, submitted, for review).

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Table 1. *Descriptive statistics of variables assessed in Study 1 and Study 2.*

Variable	Study 1			Study 2		
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	ICC	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	ICC
Level 1						
Stress with work (0-100)	48.0	29.0	-	33.4	31.5	-
Stress with close social network (0-100)	22.7	23.7	-	25.8	28.0	-
Stress with distant social network (0-100)	15.0	18.0	-	18.7	22.2	-
Daily hassles (0-100)	21.5	21.2	-	20.7	24.2	-
Negative affect (0-100)	15.6	12.9	.556	15.5	11.8	.578
Low arousing (0-100)	-	-	-	13.6	15.2	.569
High arousing (0-100)	-	-	-	18.5	14.4	.494
Positive affect (0-100)	50.0	17.9	.575	46.8	16.6	.565
Low arousing (0-100)	-	-	-	50.2	22.7	.580
High arousing (0-100)	-	-	-	36.5	20.4	.556
Level 2						
Fear of negative evaluation (3-15)	8.66	2.97	-	8.36	3.11	-
Fear of positive evaluation (0-27)	5.46	4.53	-	7.32	7.19	-

Note: ICC = Intraclass correlation.

Table 2. *Study 2: Results of the affect level hypothesis for negative and positive affect.*

Model	β (<i>SE</i>)	<i>p</i>
Negative affect level (high arousing)		
β_{01} : FNE	.206 (.510)	.688
β_{01} : FPE	-.100 (.196)	.613
Negative affect level (low arousing)		
β_{01} : FNE	-.225 (.513)	.663
β_{01} : FPE	.075 (.287)	.794
Positive affect level (high arousing)		
β_{01} : FNE	-.711 (.622)	.257
β_{01} : FPE	-.372 (.280)	.189
Positive affect level (low arousing)		
β_{01} : FNE	-1.54 (.716)	.036
β_{01} : FPE	-.199 (.371)	.594

Note: FNE = Fear of negative evaluation; FPE = Fear of positive evaluation. Emotion items were ‘irritated’/‘nervous/stressed’ for negative affect level (high arousing), ‘distressed’/‘depressed’ for negative affect level (low arousing), ‘cheerful’/‘enthusiastic’ for positive affect level (high arousing) and ‘relaxed’/ ‘calm’ for positive affect level (low arousing). Each dependent variable and each predictor (FNE and FPE, respectively) were tested in separate models.

Figure 1. Simple slopes of the affective reactivity to stress hypothesis at low (-1SD) and high (+1SD) levels of FNE and low and high levels of FPE, respectively. Scaling of the x-axis is based

on the entire range of person-mean centered scores. FNE = Fear of negative evaluation. FPE = Fear of positive evaluation.

Figure 2. Simple slopes of the affective reactivity to stress hypothesis at low (-1SD) and high (+1SD) levels of FNE and low and high levels of FPE, respectively. Scaling of the x-axis is based on the entire range of person-mean centered scores. FNE = Fear of negative evaluation. FPE = Fear of positive evaluation.

Figure 3. Simple slopes of the affective reactivity to stress hypothesis at low (-1SD) and high (+1SD) levels of FNE and FPE. Scaling of the x-axis is based on the entire range of person-mean centered scores. FNE = Fear of negative evaluation. FPE = Fear of positive evaluation.